

REVEALING HIDDEN TOPICAL HUBS AND AUTHORITIES ACROSS DIVERSE ONLINE SOCIAL NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

Finding influential users in online social networks (OSNs) is an important problem with many possible useful applications. Many methods have been proposed to identify influential users in OSNs. PageRank and HITS are two well known examples that determine influential users through link analysis. In recent years, new models that consider both content and social network links have been developed. The Hub and Authority Topic (HAT) model is one that extends HITS to identify topic-specific hubs and authorities by jointly learning hubs, authorities and topical interests from users' relationship and textual content. However, many of the previous works are confined to identifying influential users within a single OSN. These models, when applied to multiple OSNs, could not learn influential users under a common set of topics nor address platform preferences. In this paper, we therefore propose the MPHAT model, an extension of HAT, to jointly model the topic-specific hub users, authority users, their topical interests and platform preferences. We evaluate MPHAT against several existing state-of-the-art methods in three tasks: (i) modeling of topics, (ii) platform choice prediction, and (iii) link recommendation. Based on our extensive experiments in multiple OSNs settings using

synthetic datasets and real-world datasets from Twitter and Instagram, we show that MPHAT is comparable to state-of-the-art topic models in learning topics but outperforms the state-of-the-art models in platform prediction and link recommendation tasks. We also empirically demonstrate the ability of MPHAT to determine influential users within and across multiple OSNs.

1. INTRODUCTION

ONLINE social networks (OSNs), such as Face book, Twitter and Instagram, have grown phenomenally in recent years. It was reported that as of August 2017, Facebook has over 2 billion monthly active users, while Instagram and Twitter have over 700 million and 300 million monthly active user accounts respectively [1]. The vast amount of content and social data generated by these platforms has made them important resources for marketing campaigns such as diffusion of advertising messages and promotion of new products. Identifying influential users in OSNs is therefore critical to these marketing applications.

Many research works have proposed methods to identify influential users in OSNs. For example, there are works that determine users' social influence by

network centrality measures [2], [3], [4], [5]. Other works adapted HITS [6] and Page Rank [7] algorithms which were originally proposed to determine hub and authority web pages through analyzing the link structure of a web graph to identify influential users in OSNs [8], [9], [10]. Nevertheless, these existing works are either not topic specific or confined to identifying influential users within a single OSN.

Specificities are important when analyzing the hub and authority users as they provide more insights about users and reveal in which OSN platforms they are influential. To illustrate the usefulness of topic specificity, consider an example of two users, u_1 and u_2 , sharing similar ego network structures. HITS will assign u_1 and u_2 similar authority and hub scores. However, if u_1 is a popular food content contributor who is followed by many food-loving users, while u_2 is a prominent politician followed by many users interested in politics, it is more appropriate to infer that u_1 and u_2 are authority users on food-related and political topics respectively. Platform specificity is also important in identifying influential users across multiple OSNs. Suppose a user u_3 posts much food content and is followed by many food-loving users in an OSN p_1 but is less active in another OSN p_2 , i.e., u_3 contributes less content and forms fewer relationships in p_2 . While u_3 is regarded as an authority user on food-related topics, her authority on this topic is found in OSN p_1 but not p_2 .

The understanding of users' hub and authority specific to topics and platforms is vital to many important

applications such as social recommendation, viral marketing, and social sensing. For example, one can address the cold-start problem in social recommendation [11] by recommending a user u on a platform p to follow other users on p who are highly authoritative on topics that u is interested in. Similarly in marketing, companies may enhance the effectiveness of campaigns by hiring hub or authority users in topics related to the campaigns to disseminate the campaign messages so as to maximize their reach [12]. To sense social trends, one could also follow a few selected users who are hubs or authorities across different topics and on different platforms [13].

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

“Measuring user influence in twitter: The million follower fallacy.”

Directed links in social media could represent anything from intimate friendships to common interests, or even a passion for breaking news or celebrity gossip. Such directed links determine the flow of information and hence indicate a user's influence on others—a concept that is crucial in sociology and viral marketing. In this paper, using a large amount of data collected from Twitter, we present an in-depth comparison of three measures of influence: indegree, retweets, and mentions. Based on these measures, we investigate the dynamics of user influence across topics and time. We make several interesting observations. First, popular users who have high indegree are not necessarily influential in terms of spawning retweets or mentions. Second, most influential users can hold significant influence over a variety of topics. Third, influence is not gained spon-

taneously or accidentally, but through concerted effort such as limiting tweets to a single topic. We believe that these findings provide new insights for viral marketing and suggest that topological measures such as indegree alone reveals very little about the influence of a user.

“Everyone’s an influencer: quantifying influence on twitter,”

In this paper we investigate the attributes and relative influence of 1.6M Twitter users by tracking 74 million diffusion events that took place on the Twitter follower graph over a two month interval in 2009. Unsurprisingly, we find that the largest cascades tend to be generated by users who have been influential in the past and who have a large number of followers. We also find that URLs that were rated more interesting and/or elicited more positive feelings by workers on Mechanical Turk were more likely to spread. In spite of these intuitive results, however, we find that predictions of which particular user or URL will generate large cascades are relatively unreliable. We conclude, therefore, that word-of-mouth diffusion can only be harnessed reliably by targeting large numbers of potential influencers, thereby capturing average effects. Finally, we consider a family of hypothetical marketing strategies, defined by the relative cost of identifying versus compensating potential "influencers." We find that although under some circumstances, the most influential users are also the most cost-effective, under a wide range of plausible assumptions the most cost-effective performance can be realized using "ordinary influencers"---

individuals who exert average or even less-than-average influence.

“How influential are you: detecting influential bloggers in a blogging community,”

Blogging is a popular activity with high impact on marketing, shaping public opinions, and informing the world about major events from a grassroots point of view. Influential bloggers are recognized by businesses as significant forces for product promotion or demotion, and by oppressive political regimes as serious threats to their power. This paper studies the problem of identifying influential bloggers in a blogging community, BlogCatalog, by using network centrality metrics. Our analysis shows that bloggers are connected in a core-periphery network structure, with the highly influential bloggers well connected with each others forming the core, and the non-influential bloggers at the periphery. The six node centrality metrics we analyzed are highly correlated, showing that an aggregate centrality score as a measure of influence will be stable to variations in centrality metrics.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM

User relationships. Many previous works apply network centrality measures to identify influential users [4], [5], [16]. Kayes et al. [4] aggregated network centrality measures such as degree [29], betweenness [30], closeness [29] and eigenvector [31] to measure and identify influential bloggers. There are also works which extended HITS algorithm [6] to find influential users in OSNs. Romero et al. [8] proposed the influence-passivity (I-P)

algorithm to measure Twitter users' influence and passivity from their retweet activities. Gayo-Avello [15] applied HITS on Twitter follow links to identify and differentiate influential users from spammers. Shahriari and Jalili [17] modified the HITS and PageRank [7] algorithms to analyze and rank users in signed OSNs. Unlike these works, our paper extends HITS to identify topic-specific hub and authority users across multiple OSNs.

User behaviors. Besides user relationships, user behaviors, e.g., retweet and mention in Twitter, can also be used to determine influential users in OSNs. Khrabrov and Cybenko [18] adapted PageRank [7] algorithm to Twitter mention behavior to identify influential Twitter users. Silva et al. [20] employed a similar approach to find and recommend influential users based on other users' retweet activities. Aral and Walker [19] conducted a randomized experiment on Facebook to identify influential and susceptible users based on users' product sharing and adoption behaviors. User relationship and behavior. Some studies have also identified influential users by analyzing both user relationships and behaviors. Agarwal et al. [22] proposed a model that utilizes the page-linking behaviors to measure the influence of bloggers. Ghosh and Lerman [23] applied centrality measures on Digg users' friendship and voting behavior to identify influential users. Cha et al. [2] evaluated the influence of Twitter users using follower, mentions and retweets counts. Other works have also analyzed both user ego networks

and tweet activities to find influential users in Twitter [24], [25], [26], [27], [28].

Many existing works have the modeling and extraction of topics as the first and separate step in the identification of topic-specific influential users. In the simplest manner, the topics of user-generated content are first determined by performing keyword matching with a topical lexicon [3], [32], [33], [34], [36], [37], [40]. For example, in a study to identify topical authorities in Twitter, Pal and Counts [32] first extracted tweets covering three topics: "oil spill", "world cup" and "iphone" using simple substring matching before applying models to determine the topical authorities from the users' retweet behavior. Oro et al. [40] proposed social media authoritative user (SocialAU) model which includes a three-layer network (i.e., user-itemlexicon) for finding authority and hub users of a pre-defined selected topic by extending the TOPHITS, a model proposed by Kolde et al [46] to analyze a semantic graph that combines anchor text with the hyperlink structure of the web.

Disadvantages

- There is less security on outsourced data due to lack of Generative Process for MPHAT Model.
- Direct The system is less secured due to absence of Multiple Platforms Link Recommendation.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

In this work, we aim to model topic and platform specific hub and authority users across multiple OSNs. A simple approach

for this could be to first apply the existing topic specific hub and authority models (e.g. HAT [14]) on multiple OSNs separately, followed by comparing the list of top topical authority and hub users identified in the different OSNs. However, the topics separately learned from different platforms may not be comparable and thus making it is hard to compare users' hub and authority across the OSNs. Another possible approach that overcomes the incomparability of latent topics learned from the different OSNs is to combine the multiple OSN datasets and learn the users' topics, hub and authority scores from the single combined dataset. For example, we can first combine a user u 's generated

posts and links from OSNs p_1 and p_2 into a single combined dataset and then apply HAT on the combined dataset. The problem with this approach is that it assumes u has identical hub and authority scores in the two platforms. In other words, if u is an authority on food-related topic in platform p_1 , she is also the food authority in platform p_2 . In the real-world context, this assumption does not hold as u might be more popular in one platform than the other. We thus propose Multiple Platforms Hub and Authority Topic (MPHAT) model to learn users' topical interests, platform preferences, topic-specific hub and authority scores simultaneously.

We first develop a process for generating both users' content and links in the context of multiple OSNs. We then describe the parameters learning steps of MPHAT. To evaluate MPHAT, we conduct experiments

on both real-world and synthetic datasets. For experiments on real-world dataset, we evaluate MPHAT on (i) its effectiveness in learning topics from user generated content, (ii) its ability to predict the platform choice of users' publish post, and (iii) its ability to recommend platform-specific topical influential users through link prediction in a multiple OSNs setting. On synthetic datasets, we further evaluate MPHAT's ability to recover platform-specific topical hub and authority users provided by the ground truth.

Advantages

_ We propose a topic-based model, Multiple Platforms Hub and Authority Topic (MPHAT) model, which to the best of our knowledge, is the first model that jointly learns user topics, platform preferences, hub and authority users across multiple online social networks.

_ We apply the MPHAT model on real-world datasets and demonstrate that (a) MPHAT is comparable to state-of-the-art topic models in learning topics from user generated content, and (b) MPHAT outperforms other models in user link recommendation tasks for both single and multiple platform settings. Empirically, we also applied MPHAT to identify topic-specific hubs and authorities across Instagram and Twitter.

_ We also conduct experiments on synthetic datasets to verify the effectiveness of MPHAT in identifying platform-specific topical hubs and authorities under different dataset parameter settings.

5. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

6. IMPLEMENTATION

Modules

OSN Server

In this module, the Service Provider has to login by using valid user name and password. After login successful he can do some operations such as Login, View All Users And Authorize, View Friend Request and Response, View All User Posts, View All Posts Recommended Details, View All Hidden Topics Details, View Posts Scores Results.

View and Authorize Users

In this module, the admin can view the list of users who all registered. In this, the admin can view the user's details such as, user name, email, address and admin authorizes the users.

End User

In this module, there are n numbers of users are present. User should register before doing any operations. Once user registers, their details will be stored to the database. After registration successful, he has to login by using authorized user name and password. Once Login is successful user will do some operations like Register and Login, My Profile View All Users and Follow, View All My Friends List, Add Post, View All My Posts, Search Post, View All My Friends Posts, View All Recommended Posts..

7. SCREENSHOTS

8. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

In this paper, we have proposed a novel generative model called Multiple Platform

Hub and Authority Topic (MPHAT) model, which jointly models user's topic specific hubs authorities, interests and platform preferences. We evaluated MPHAT using synthetic and real-world datasets and benchmarked against the state-of-the art. Our experiments on Twitter and Instagram datasets show that our proposed MPHAT outperforms LDA and achieves comparable results as TW LDA in topic modeling. On platform prediction, MPHAT outperforms the TW LDA baseline method and is able to predict which platform a user would publish his or her posts with reasonable accuracy. On link recommendation, MPHAT outperforms the baseline methods in MRR by at least 10%. We have empirically shown that MPHAT is able to identify hub and authority users within and across Twitter and Instagram for different topics. Our experiments on synthetic datasets also show that our proposed model outperforms baseline method in identifying hub and authority users in multiple OSNs setting.

For future works, we would like to extend our model to include non-topical relationship among users. Currently, our model assumes that all links among users are topical although a user may follow each other for social reasons (e.g., they are friends).

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